

Digital health access and utilisation by women in Aotearoa New Zealand: Protocol for a scoping review.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, health is a state of complete physical, social, and mental well-being (1). For nearly 80 years, it has been recognised as a fundamental human right that should be accessible to all, irrespective of gender, ethnicity, religion, geographical location, or any other factor (1)(2). However, this right has not been the reality for many women across the globe, especially those from ethnic minority groups, as they often experience difficulties with accessing and utilising health services, commonly resulting in poorer health outcomes (3)(4).

Aotearoa New Zealand, is a multicultural country with a rich diversity of ethnic groups within its communities (5). According to Statistics New Zealand, there are over 160 ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand, of which six are classified as level one or major (5)(6). These major ethnicity categories are Middle Eastern, Latin American, African (MELAA), Māori, Pasifika, European, Asian, and Others (5). Studies have highlighted that among these ethnic groups, non-European (Māori, MELAA, Pasifika, Asian) women commonly experience structural, attitudinal, and cultural barriers in accessing and utilising health services, with resultant poor experiences and outcomes (7)(8)(9)(10)(11).

Digital health is an evolving area in clinical practice and research that involves the convergence of health and technology, where individual and population health and well-being remain the focus, and the technology is employed as a tool to facilitate disease prevention, manage illnesses, and improve the overall quality of life (12). First described more than 20 years ago as the interaction between the interactive media (World Wide Web and Internet) and medical care (13), digital health has evolved to include telemedicine, telehealth, health information technology, mobile health, wearable devices, software, computing platforms, machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms (14) (15). The World Health Organization in 2018 highlighted the importance of digital health as a potent tool in the provision of people-centred health care, reduction of health inequity, and improvement of gender equity when utilised in combination with traditional face-to-face health care delivery models (16), opening opportunities for improvement in health outcomes for women.

In 2019, the New Zealand telehealth report highlighted that 1,324 telehealth services across all 20 District Health Boards were already using, planning to use, or piloting digital health services (17). Disciplines with established digital health services for optimal patient care included paediatrics, mental health, adult medicine, allied and women's health (17). Despite previous studies highlighting

the value of digital health technologies in obtaining health information (18), strengthening healthy diet choices (19), and improving maternal and child outcomes (20), little is known about how women in Aotearoa New Zealand engage with these opportunities to improve their health and well-being.

To determine how women in Aotearoa New Zealand engage with digital health services, a scoping review will be undertaken to explore how women from different ethnic identities access and utilise digital health services. Factors that impede and enhance digital health access and utilisation among these women will also be explored. Furthermore, possible challenges and opportunities for equitable health policy formulation amongst women from these ethnic groups will be investigated. A scoping review is important for examining available evidence in specific areas, identifying knowledge gaps, establishing research priorities, and highlighting issues relevant to policymakers (21) (22), hence apt for this study.

Study aim

To explore how women from different ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand access and utilise digital health technologies, a relatively understudied area.

Methods

The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) scoping review methodological framework (23) will be used for this review.

Review questions

To understand how women in Aotearoa New Zealand access and utilise digital health technologies, the following review questions will be applied:

1. Do women in Aotearoa New Zealand access and utilise digital health technologies?
2. What types of digital health technologies do women in Aotearoa New Zealand access and utilise?
3. What are the barriers to accessing and utilising digital health technologies for women in Aotearoa New Zealand?
4. What are the facilitators for accessing and utilising digital health technologies for women in Aotearoa New Zealand?
5. Are there differences regarding access, utilisation, barriers encountered, and facilitators to digital health technologies engagement among women from different ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand?

Participants

The review will focus on literature covering research that includes women from all ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand.

Concept

Digital health technologies are platforms where technology intersects with health to improve health and well-being (12). For this study, digital health technologies will include:

- 1) Telehealth or telemedicine: use of videoconferencing, emails, text messages, online patient portals, text messages, and phone calls for non-clinical services (i.e., online health education resources) and medical care (i.e., virtual consultations with health care providers).
- 2) Wearable devices and sensors that record and send patient health information to health care providers, including wellness mobile applications, diet, and fitness trackers.
- 3) Mobile phones and wellness applications for managing health and wellbeing, i.e., health, diet, exercise, and fitness applications.
- 4) Online platforms to seek health information and support women in making healthy choices, i.e., internet, Facebook.

Context

The review will focus on digital health utilisation among women from all ethnic groups in Aotearoa New Zealand in non-clinical settings for disease prevention and health promotion and those employing digital technologies in clinical settings for managing conditions will be included.

Inclusion criteria.

- Studies conducted on adult women (aged 16 years and above or as defined by authors in included studies).
- All study designs and grey literature.
- Publications in English language.
- Studies conducted in Aotearoa New Zealand. Studies conducted across several countries including Aotearoa New Zealand will also be included if analysis was done by countries and results from women in Aotearoa New Zealand are reported separately.
- No limit to publication dates.

Exclusion criteria.

- Study protocols.
- Publications not in English.
- Abstracts (when full text is not available).
- Literature that has both men and women.

Search strategy

A three-step comprehensive search strategy will be developed with one of the University of Auckland's Research Services Advisors. The first search of keywords and medical subject headings (MeSH) terms will be conducted in Medline (Ovid) and PsycINFO databases to identify in the title and abstract other relevant keywords, synonyms, and MESH terms. After that, the search will include all pre-specified databases using all identified relevant words (Keywords, Synonyms, MeSH terms) from the first search. For the third stage, a search of the reference list of identified relevant records for additional papers will be undertaken.

Information sources

The search will be conducted in the following databases and trial registries from inception until the search date- Medline (Ovid), Scopus, PsycINFO, EMBASE, Cochrane Library, Australian and New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry (www.anzctr.org.au), and Informit New Zealand Collection for relevant publications, including grey literature from New Zealand government and non-government websites. Multiple articles from a single study will be combined and the most recent publication from the series will be chosen as the primary publication (24).

Screening and selecting literature.

Studies identified from the search strategy will be imported into Rayyan software (25) to ensure a systematic review to identify eligible studies. Two reviewers will independently conduct a two-step screening process. Firstly, the title and abstracts will be screened, followed by a full-text screening. Any discrepancies will be resolved with discussion between the two independent reviewers.

Data extraction and management.

Two reviewers will independently extract relevant data using a pre-designed data extraction form, and discrepancies will be resolved with discussion. Data extracted will include the author(s), year of publication, location of study, study aim(s), sample size, ethnicity, methodology, type of digital health technology, setting for the use of digital health (non-clinical, clinical [public or private], preventative or therapeutic purposes), main findings/conclusions, impact of utilising digital health technology on health outcomes, barriers to accessing and utilising digital health technologies, factors facilitating access to and utilization of digital health technologies. We will synthesise findings for the review questions in a tabular format accompanied by narrative prose.

Quality of included studies.

A formal assessment of the methodological quality (risk of bias) of included studies will not be undertaken as scoping reviews are designed to present an overview of available evidence in an area irrespective of methodological quality (23)(26).

Reporting

The review will be reported with the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews checklist (26).

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